

AN ASSESSMENT OF FINANCIAL MANAGEMENT BEHAVIOR AND FINANCIAL WELL-BEING AMONG HEALTHCARE WORKERS

Nurperihan Tosun^{1*}, Sermed Doğan²

Keywords

Healthcare Workers,

Financial Management Behavior,

Financial Well-Being,

Financial Sustainability

ABSTRACT

While healthcare workers provide care under demanding working conditions, they are relatively more financially vulnerable compared to other occupational groups. The ability to plan, monitor, and rationally manage future financial processes plays a decisive role in the psychosocial well-being of healthcare professionals. In this regard, the aim of this study is to examine the relationship between financial management behavior and financial well-being among healthcare workers. A systematic literature review was employed to explore the evolution of these concepts over time and to identify related thematic areas. In this study, the Web of Science database was used, and a dataset of 567 articles was compiled by applying inclusion and exclusion criteria. The articles in the dataset were evaluated in terms of their distribution by year and growth rate, the list of most frequently used keywords, their disciplinary distribution, and information on the most-cited study. The analysis revealed that the number of articles published on this topic has increased over the years, showing a significant growth rate of 13.65%. The keywords most closely associated with these concepts were found to be COVID-19, mental health, financial stress, quality of life, and financial literacy. Furthermore, the articles were published primarily in the fields of business, economics, and family studies. However, the most highly cited study (544 out of 3,240, or 16.79%) on the topic of financial well-being focuses on key points such as financial security, financial control, future expectations, and maintaining living standards. In conclusion, the expectation that healthcare workers will manage financial processes and maintain their well-being amid the intense and complex demands of their professional lives emerges as a critical factor in sustaining work-life balance. At the same time, financial management and well-being are associated not only with economic factors but also with psychosocial variables such as mental health, life satisfaction, depression, stress, and family.

INTRODUCTION

Today, competition is intensifying across all sectors, including healthcare. By their nature, healthcare services are becoming increasingly complex and dynamic, while also being shaped by financial uncertainties, limited resources, ongoing healthcare reforms, stricter regulations, and rapid technological advancements. In this challenging environment, healthcare managers and professionals play a key role in ensuring institutional success by managing costs and improving operational efficiency. Accordingly, financial awareness and effective management behaviors particularly in areas such as inventory control, workforce planning, and waste reduction have become increasingly important. These competencies not only support efficient use of organizational resources but also contribute to the financial well-being of individuals working within the healthcare system^{1,2}.

Finance refers to the financial resources available to a healthcare institution, whereas funding describes the processes through which these resources are obtained to meet the institution's financial needs³. Healthcare institutions need to manage their financial resources effectively and accurately to achieve their goals. Today, both changes in economic conditions and rapid developments in the healthcare sector have made this management a necessity rather than a choice. Financial sustainability is considered the capacity of institutions, organizations, and economies not only to maintain their current financial health but also to securely meet their long-term liabilities without jeopardizing their future assets. Considering financial management behaviors and financial well-being together in healthcare professionals offers an important area of assessment for both individual well-being and the sustainability of healthcare systems⁴.

Volume: 4

Issue: 2

Page: 227– 234

Received: 17.02.2026

Accepted: 15.06.2026

Available online: 30.06.2026

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.21065709

Financial management encompasses all processes of planning, organizing, executing, coordinating, and controlling finances⁵. Financial behavior management is the process by which individuals use their financial resources effectively and efficiently, and simultaneously direct these resources towards more profitable and lower-risk areas⁶. Financial management behavior refers to the process by which individuals direct their actions such as shopping, spending, saving, and investing, depending on their level of financial awareness. In this process, individuals are expected to act carefully and consciously, making beneficial decisions and developing saving and investment habits. At the same time, carefully evaluating and properly managing financial decisions such as borrowing and using credit is also part of financial management behavior⁷.

Within the framework of behavioral finance, financial well-being is a state that can vary from person to person depending on individuals' concerns about the future and how secure they feel. Financial well-being is defined as the alignment between individuals' current standard of living and the standard of living they expect and aspire to achieve in the future, as well as their perception of their ability to maintain financial freedom. In this regard, it is emphasized that the concept has a subjective nature⁸. Financial well-being is closely associated with how individuals manage their personal finances. Individuals who are able to manage their income and expenses in a responsible and balanced manner are more likely to experience greater financial well-being and, consequently, higher levels of overall life satisfaction⁹. There is a strong reciprocal relationship between a person's health status and financial well-being. Individuals who are financially better off generally have better health levels because they have easier access to healthcare and more favorable living conditions. On the other hand, economic difficulties can limit individuals' access to necessary healthcare services, leading to a negative trend in their health status¹⁰.

Healthcare workers experience high levels of stress due to long working hours, heavy workloads, and physically and emotionally demanding working conditions. This increases the risk of burnout and can negatively impact both employee well-being and the quality of service. Therefore, reducing stress among healthcare workers has long been a significant focus of both academic research and health policies. Furthermore,

studies have shown that financial status can also influence work-related stress, further highlighting the importance of financial well-being and financial management behaviors for healthcare workers^{11,12,13}. According to the WHO, fair compensation, safe working conditions, and financial protection for healthcare workers are fundamental requirements for the sustainability of health systems. Insufficient financial support and low wages reduce the motivation of the healthcare workforce and threaten the long-term sustainability of the system^{14,15}.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study focuses on financial management behavior and financial well-being among healthcare workers. Studies conducted on these topics were examined using systematic literature review and bibliometric analysis methods. To determine how these topics have changed over time, identify relationships, and establish future trends, the document analysis method was chosen for the systematic literature review. This analytical method provides an opportunity for a broad and in-depth examination of the existing literature. Consequently, a dataset was created by following specific procedures to enable a detailed evaluation of the existing literature within the scope of this study.

In line with the study's objective, a dataset search was first conducted. The Web of Science database was used to access the dataset. The study aimed to include all data published up to the year 2025. Accordingly, the dataset covers studies published between 1992—the year the first study was conducted—and 2025. The concepts “financial management behavior,” “financial well-being,” and “health” were searched together as keywords. To ensure that no studies in the database were overlooked, the search was conducted in the title, abstract, and keyword sections. As a result of the search, 631 studies were identified. The screening process and study selection are presented in the PRISMA flow diagram (Figure 1). The following criteria were applied to the total dataset: the study must be a journal article, published in English, and indexed in the Social Sciences Citation Index, Science Citation Index Expanded, or Emerging Sources Citation Index. After applying these restrictions, a dataset of 567 journal articles was obtained. The criteria are illustrated in Figure 1 as a PRISMA flow diagram.

Figure 1. PRISMA Flow Diagram

RESULTS

To examine publication trends in financial management behavior and financial well-being in the healthcare sector, the annual growth rate was calculated. The calculation was based on the first and the most recent publication years, corresponding to a 34-year period. Accordingly¹⁶, the annual growth rate was calculated using the following formula: $\text{Growth rate} = (\text{number of publications in the last year} \div \text{number of publications in the first year})^{1/(\text{last year} - \text{first year})} - 1 \times 100$. The analysis showed that the annual growth rate of publications on financial management behavior and financial well-being in the healthcare sector was 13.65%. A particularly marked increase was observed between 2015 and 2025, during which the growth rate reached 24.10%. Publications published during this period accounted for 87.83% (498/567) of all included articles.

According to the findings, the most dominant field in the literature is "Business & Economics," accounting for 25%. While this is an expected result given the nature of financial

processes, the significant distribution within the healthcare sector is noteworthy. "Public, Environmental & Occupational Health," which directly encompasses healthcare systems and service delivery, ranks second with 16%, followed by "Health Care Sciences & Services" with 12%. The combined total of these two healthcare-focused categories (28%) clearly demonstrates the weight of the subject in the healthcare management and occupational health literature.

Figure 2 presents the results of a keyword co-occurrence network analysis conducted to identify the relationships between the most frequently used keywords in the included articles and the conceptual focal points in the literature. The node sizes on the map indicate the frequency of occurrence of the concepts, while the thickness of the lines shows the strength of their simultaneous treatment in the articles. The analysis revealed different clustering focuses centered around the concept of "financial well-being," which acts as the largest node in the literature and serves as a bridge connecting all sub-themes.

Graph 1. Distribution of articles by year

Graph 2. Distribution of bibliometric data by field

Figure 2. Keyword Co-occurrence Network Analysis of the Included Studies

One of these clusters, the red cluster located in the upper part of the map, focuses on financial literacy, financial knowledge, and financial stress, reflecting both the mechanisms of financial systems and individuals' subjective perceptions of budgeting. This cluster highlights the critical role of financial literacy in shaping individuals' life satisfaction. The green cluster on the right side of the map, which includes quality of life and financial toxicity, indicates that financial difficulties are discussed as factors that negatively affect individuals' perceived health status and overall standard of living. In contrast, the blue cluster on the left is associated with structural determinants such as debt and poverty, emphasizing the broader socioeconomic context of financial well-being.

The clusters of purple and yellow concentrated in the lower and lower-left quadrants of the map clearly illustrate the psychosocial effects of financial circumstances on individuals. The central position of the "mental health," "depression," "anxiety," and "psychological distress" nodes indicates a strong

link between financial vulnerability and mental health issues. One of the striking findings on the map is the strong connections established by the "COVID-19" node with both financial stress and mental health variables. This indicates that the pandemic did not merely create a physical health crisis but also negatively impacted financial well-being, thereby exerting significant pressure on psychological well-being.

In terms of publication volume, the "Journal of Family and Economic Issues" ranks first with 12 articles (2.99%). This journal also ranks first in impact factor (Ranking by total number of citations) with a total of 535 citations (3.82%), proving its status as the most established and referenced journal in the field. "BMC Public Health" ranks second with 11 articles (2.74%), followed by "International Journal of Bank Marketing" and "Frontiers in Public Health" with 9 articles each (2.24%). "Journal of Consumer Affairs" is in fifth place with 8 articles (1.99%).

Table 1. Top Five Journals Ranked by Number of Publications and Citation Counts

Journals	Ranking by total number of articles	Articles ^a , n (%)	Sorted by total number of citations	Citation ^b , n (%)
Journal of family and economic issues	1	12 (2.99)	1	535 (3.82)
BMC public health	2	11 (2.74)	3	121 (0.86)
International journal of bank marketing	3	9 (2.24)	4	39 (0.28)
Frontiers in public health	4	9 (2.24)	2	267 (1.92)
Journal of consumer affairs	5	8 (1.99)	5	25 (0.18)
^a n=402 ^b n=13.998				

a Number of articles published in the top five journals (n=402)

A systematic literature review reveals that the field of financial well-being has a balanced structure shaped by both theoretical and empirical research. An evaluation of the top 10 most cited

studies shows that the conceptual foundation of the field is built upon strong review articles, followed by quantitative research tested in the field.

Table 2. Characteristics of the 10 Most-Cited Articles

Article	Author(s)	Citation Count	Methodological Approach	
			Research Method	Data Collection Method
Financial well-being: A conceptualization and research agenda	Brüggen, EC; Hogreve, J; Holmlund, M; Kabadayi, S; Löfgren, M	544	Conceptual approach	Literature review
How Am I Doing? Perceived Financial Well-Being, Its Potential Antecedents, and Its Relation to Overall Well-Being	Netemeyer, RG; Warmath, D; Fernandes, D; Lynch, JG	495	Quantitative	Survey
Pathways to life success: A conceptual model of financial well-being for young adults	Shim, S; Xiao, JJ; Barber, BL; Lyons, AC	404	Quantitative	Online survey
Psychosocial Care for Family Caregivers of Patients With Cancer	Northouse, L; Williams, AL; Given, B; McCorkle, R	396	Review	Literature review
Financial toxicity in cancer care: Prevalence, causes, consequences, and reduction strategies	Lentz, R; Benson, AB; Kircher, S	279	Review	Literature review
Decision making in the ageing brain: changes in affective and motivational circuits	Samanez-Larkin, GR; Knutson, B	251	Review	Literature review
Does self-control predict financial behavior and financial well-being?	Strömbäck, C; Lind, T; Skagerlund, K; Västfjäll, D; Tinghög, G	250	Quantitative	Survey
Financial Behaviors and Financial Well-Being of College Students: Evidence from a National Survey	Gutter, M; Copur, Z	221	Quantitative	Online survey
Debt and depression	Bridges, S; Disney, R	217	Quantitative	Survey
Financial toxicity and implications for cancer care in the era of molecular and immune therapies	Tran, G; Zafar, SY	183	Review	Literature review

According to Table 1, the concentration of publications and citations in a relatively small number of journals suggests that financial management behavior and financial well-being have become established research themes within both healthcare and social science disciplines.

Table 2 shows that studies with the highest impact factors did not treat financial well-being solely as an economic concept, but rather evaluated it in relation to different variables such as life satisfaction, self-control, mental health, indebtedness, and financial toxicity. This indicates that the concept of financial well-being has evolved over time from a structure that only explains individual financial behavior to an interdisciplinary research field integrating with psychology, health, and behavioral sciences.

The most highly cited study, with 544 citations, is the article by Brügger et al. (2017) titled “Financial well-being: A conceptualization and research agenda”¹⁷. This conceptual work has clarified the theoretical framework of financial well-being and has served as a key reference point for subsequent research. It is followed by Netemeyer et al. (495 citations)¹⁸ and Shim et al. (404 citations)¹⁹. The common focus of these studies is on the perceptual dimensions of financial well-being, its relationship with life satisfaction, and its developmental aspects, particularly among young adults.

From a methodological perspective, it is noteworthy that half of the most cited studies have a quantitative research design and mostly use survey-based data collection methods. The other half consists of conceptual and review studies. This indicates that the field initially took shape theoretically, but over time, it has become more empirically grounded, supported by field data.

CONCLUSION

It is well known that healthcare workers provide care under intense and highly stressful professional conditions and are therefore financially more vulnerable than other occupational groups. The literature suggests that the ability to plan, control, and rationally manage financial processes has a significant impact on the psychosocial well-being of healthcare professionals^{4,14,15}. Accordingly, this study aimed to evaluate the relationship between financial management behavior and financial well-being among healthcare workers. When the

findings are evaluated collectively, it is observed that the literature on financial management behavior and financial well-being has followed a fluctuating development trajectory over the past thirty years, characterized by distinct spikes during certain periods rather than a steady increase. This suggests that the topic has become more visible, particularly in recent years, alongside growing academic and societal interest.

Keyword co-occurrence analysis, meanwhile, reveals that the concept of “financial well-being” occupies a central position in the literature and serves as a fundamental focal point linking different research themes. While themes such as financial literacy, financial knowledge, and financial stress which explain an individual’s financial awareness and subjective experience come to the fore around this central concept, concepts such as quality of life and financial toxicity highlight the impact of financial status on one’s overall perception of life. On the other hand, it is noteworthy that structural variables such as indebtedness and poverty are among the key determinants associated with financial well-being.

The findings further indicate that financial vulnerability is not limited to economic outcomes but is strongly associated with psychosocial outcomes such as mental health, anxiety, depression, and psychological distress. In particular, the strong link between the COVID-19 pandemic and both financial stress and mental health indicators clearly demonstrates the multidimensional impact of the pandemic on financial well-being^{20,21}.

Citation analyses derived from a systematic literature review, meanwhile, indicate that the field has developed in a balanced manner through both conceptual and empirical studies. A significant portion of the studies with the greatest impact consists of review articles that form the conceptual framework of financial well-being, followed by field studies that quantitatively test individuals’ financial well-being and related variables. This finding suggests that the field initially went through a process of conceptual clarification and, over time, has evolved into a more mature research area, strengthened by empirical data.

In conclusion, financial management behavior and financial well-being stand out as important concepts that can affect not only the economic situation but also the professional and psychosocial well-being of healthcare professionals. The fact that the current literature consists mainly of cross-sectional

studies indicates the need for longitudinal research to reveal the changes in this relationship over time. Furthermore, it is considered that multicenter studies conducted in different healthcare systems will make significant contributions to the development of institutional practices and policies aimed at supporting financial well-being.

The current literature appears to consist predominantly of quantitative, survey-based, and cross-sectional studies. Therefore, future studies should incorporate longitudinal research designs that can track changes in healthcare workers' financial management behaviors and financial well-being over time. Furthermore, it is recommended that qualitative or mixed-methods studies based on in-depth interviews be increased to provide a more comprehensive perspective on these processes.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Ethical Approval Statement

Ethics committee approval is not required as there is no human or animal research.

REFERENCES

- Lee J, Kim Y, Kim E. Challenges and strategies for enhancing nurse managers' financial management competencies: a scoping review. *J Nurs Manag.* 2026;2026(1):7525983.
- Meyers RC, Kottapalli P. Strategic planning and aggressiveness in healthcare: navigating uncertainty for organizational success. *Healthc Strategy Rev.* 2025;1(3):42–54.
- Şakar T, Yaman K. Mersin ilinde serbest eczacıların finansal okuryazarlık ile finansal yönetim davranışı arasındaki ilişkinin incelenmesi. *Mersin Univ Sag Bilim Derg.* 2024;17(2):289–300.
- Ismail HA, Kotp MH, Basyouny HAA, Abd Elmoaty AEE, Hendy A, Ibrahim RK, et al. Empowering nurse leaders: leveraging financial management practices to foster sustainable healthcare—a mixed-methods study. *BMC Nurs.* 2025;24(1):335.
- Akbulut Y, Gökteş B. Sağlık kurumlarında finansal yönetimin kapsamı. In: Ağırbaş İ, editor. *Sağlık Kurumlarında Finansal Yönetim.* 1st ed. Eskişehir: Anadolu Üniversitesi Yayını; 2013. p. 4. ISBN: 978-975-06-1528-3.
- Soydaş ŞS. Finansal bilgi düzeyinin finansal yönetim davranışı ve yatırım davranışına etkisi. *İşletme Araştırmaları Dergisi.* 2023;15(4):2816–2822.
- Güvemli B, Meydan S. Üniversite öğrencilerinin finansal davranışları ve finansal tutumları: Trakya Üniversitesi örneği. *Muhasebe Finansman Derg.* 2019;(Özel Sayı):171–184.
- Önem HB. Finansal iyi oluş düzeyine demografik faktörlerin etkisi: üniversite personeli üzerine bir uygulama. *Oltu Beşeri Sos Bilim Derg.* 2022;3(1):46–51.
- Özgüner M, Özdemir A. Finansal iyilik halinin yaşam doyumuna etkisi. *J Soc Sci.* 2020;31(31):460–470.
- Prawitz A, Garman ET, Sorhaindo B, O'Neill B, Kim J, Drentea P. In Charge financial distress/financial well-being scale: development, administration, and score interpretation. *J Financ Couns Plan.* 2006;17(1).
- Çamkerten S, Tatar A, Saltukoğlu G. Sağlık çalışanlarının stres düzeylerinin incelenmesi. *Sağlık Akademisyenleri Derg.* 2020;7(4):257–265.
- Kınış Z, Boztosun D. Sağlık çalışanlarının finansal iyi hal durumlarının iş performansına etkisinin incelenmesi: Kayseri ili örneği. *19 Mayıs Sos Bilim Derg.* 2022;3(4):379–392.
- Koramşa A, Yaman K. Sağlık çalışanlarının çalışma koşulları ve motivasyonları ile finansal durumları arasındaki ilişkinin incelenmesi: Mersin Üniversitesi Hastanesi örneği. *Mersin Univ Sos Bilim Enst Derg.* 2024;7(2):81–93.
- World Health Organization. Working for health and growth: investing in the health workforce. Geneva: WHO; 2016. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/handle/10665/250047>
- World Health Organization, International Labour Organization, Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development. Working for health: employment and economic growth in the health sector. Geneva: WHO; 2017.
- Guo Y, Hao Z, Zhao S, Gong J, Yang F. Artificial intelligence in health care: bibliometric analysis. *J Med Internet Res.* 2020;22(7):e18228
- Brüggen EC, Hogreve J, Holmlund M, Kabadayi S, Löfgren M. Financial well-being: A conceptualization and research agenda. *J Bus Res.* 2017;79:228–237.
- Netemeyer RG, Warmath D, Fernandes D, Lynch JG Jr. How am I doing? Perceived financial well-being, its potential antecedents, and its relation to overall well-being. *J Consum Res.* 2018;45(1):68–89.
- Shim S, Xiao JJ, Barber BL, Lyons AC. Pathways to life success: A conceptual model of financial well-being for young adults. *J Appl Dev Psychol.* 2009;30(6):708–723.
- Vieira KM, Potrich ACG, Bressan AA, Klein LL. Loss of financial well-being in the COVID-19 pandemic: Does job stability make a difference? *J Behav Exp Finance.* 2021;31:100554.
- Xiong J, Lipsitz O, Nasri F, Lui LMW, Gill H, Phan L, et al. Impact of COVID-19 pandemic on mental health in the general population: A systematic review. *J Affect Disord.* 2020;277:55–64.